

Cuadro 1: Primary studies included in the review.

Id	Paper	Year	Author	Ref.
PS1	Towards Automated Detection of Inline Code Comment Smells	2025	Oztas, I.; Torun, U. B.; Tüzün, E.	[1]
PS2	Automated Inline Comment Smell Detection and Repair with LLMs	2025	Çağlar, H. K.; Çağlar, S.; Tüzün, E.	[2]
PS3	Taxonomy of Inline Code Comment Smells	2024	Jabrayilzade, E.; Yurtoğlu, A.; Tüzün, E.	[3]
PS4	Using Transformer-based Pre-trained Language Model for Automated Evaluation of Comments to Aid Software Maintenance	2022	Paul, D.; Biswas, B.; Paul, R.	[4]
PS5	Do automatic comment generation techniques fall short? Exploring the influence of method dependencies on code understanding	2025	Billah, M. M.; Rahman, M. S.; Roy, B.	[5]
PS6	Reliable Inline Code Documentation with LLMs: Fine-Grained Evaluation of Comment Quality and Coverage	2025	Patil, R.; Tirodkar, G.; Gafane, S.	[6]
PS7	Autogenics: Automated generation of context-aware inline comments for code snippets on programming Q&A sites using LLM	2024	Bappon, S. D.; Mondal, S.; Roy, B.	[7]
PS8	Leveraging Language Models for Code Comment Classification	2023	Patel, J. T.	[8]
PS9	An empirical study on the quality assessment of code comments generated by large language models for different programming paradigms	2024	Li, P.; Liu, W.; Zheng, Q.	[9]
PS10	Towards efficient code documentation: A dataset for automated comment generation in Java	2024	Cherradi, M.; Khamjane, A.; Ragragui, A.	[10]
PS11	Automated code comments generation using large language models: Empirical evaluation of T5 and BART	2025	Ghale, D. P.; Dabbagh, M.	[11]
PS12	Deep code-comment understanding and assessment	2019	Wang, D.; Guo, Y.; Dong, W.; Wang, Z.; Liu, H.; Li, S.	[12]
PS13	Detecting Inline Code Comment Smells Leveraging CodeBERT Model	2026	Mahmood, S.	[13]
PS14	The CodeLLM Handshake: Smarter Maintenance Through AI	2026	Deshpande, A.; Maji, A.; Mondol, D.; Das, P. P.; Clough, P. D.; Majumdar, S.	[14]
PS15	Suggesting Comment Completions for Python using Neural Language Models	2020	Ciurumelea, A.; Proksch, S.; Gall, H. C.	[15]
PS16	An empirical study on the effectiveness of large language models for SATD identification and classification	2024	Sheikhaei, M. S.; Tian, Y.; Wang, S.; Xu, B.	[16]
PS17	LLMUpdater: Automatic comment synchronization via edit model guided LLMs	2026	Yang, H.; Xie, Q.; Cai, S.; et al.	[17]
PS18	R ² ComSync: improving code-comment synchronization with in-context learning and reranking	2026	Yang, Z.; Lin, H.; Yu, X.; Keung, J. W.; Liu, S.; Chan, P. Y. P.; Sun, Y.; Zhang, F.	[18]
PS19	Few-shot training LLMs for project-specific code-summarization	2023	Ahmed, T.; Devanbu, P.	[19]
PS20	Adversarial Robustness of Deep Code Comment Generation	2022	Zhou, Y.; Zhang, X.; Shen, J.; Han, T.; Chen, T.; Gall, H.	[20]
PS21	DLCoG: A Novel Framework for Dual-Level Code Comment Generation Based on Semantic Segmentation and In-Context Learning	2025	Zhang, Z.; Yang, H.; Yan, Q.; Yan, H.; Min, W.; Wei, Z.; Kuang, L.; Xia, Y.	[21]
PS22	Detecting Code Comment Inconsistencies using LLM and Program Analysis	2024	Zhang, Y.	[22]
PS23	Code Comment Classification with Data Augmentation and Transformer-Based Models	2025	Rahman, M.; Siddiq, M. L.	[23]
PS24	Less Is More: DocString Compression in Code Generation	2026	Yang, G.; Zhou, Y.; Cheng, W.; Zhang, X.; Chen, X.; Zhuo, T. Y.; Liu, K.; Zhou, X.; Lo, D.; Chen, T.	[24]
PS25	SEOCD: Detecting obsolete code comments by fusing semantic features and expert features	2025	Cui, Z.; Liu, S.; Li, L.; Zheng, L.	[25]

Cuadro 2: Primary studies incorporated through snowballing.

Id	Paper	Year	Author	Origin	Ref.
PS26	Large Language Models are Few-Shot Summarizers: Multi-Intent Comment Generation via In-Context Learning	2024	Geng, M.; Wang, S.; Dong, D.; Wang, H.; Li, G.; Jin, Z.; Mao, X.; Liao, X.	PS17	[26]
PS27	A comparative study on method comment and inline comment	2023	Huang, Y.; Guo, H.; Ding, X.; Shu, J.; Chen, X.; Luo, X.; et al.	PS2	[27]
PS28	DocChecker: Bootstrapping Code Large Language Model for Detecting and Resolving Code-Comment Inconsistencies	2024	Dau, A.; Guo, J. L.; Bui, N.	PS2	[28]

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Id	Paper	Year	Author	Origin	Ref.
PS29	Snippet Comment Generation Based on Code Context Expansion	2023	Guo, H.; Chen, X.; Huang, Y.; Wang, Y.; Ding, X.; Zheng, Z.; Zhou, X.; Dai, H.	PS21	[29]
PS30	Retrieve and refine: exemplar-based neural comment generation	2021	Wei, B.; Li, Y.; Li, G.; Xia, X.; Jin, Z.	PS26	[30]

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